

Repository or database	URL/Reference	Geoscientific data from Svalbard included?	Harvested by SIOS?
Global thematic databases			
Zircon U-Th-Pb global Geochron dataset	Wu et al. (2023)	yes	no
Global geochronological database	http://geochron.org/	yes	no
Global palaeomagnetic library	https://paleomagnetism.org/library/ Koymans et al. (2020)	no	no
USGS Geochronological and Thermochronological data	Hillenbrand et al. (2023) https://doi.org/10.5066/P9RZNPIF	no	no
The Global Heat Flow Database	http://ihfc-iugg.org/products/global-heat-flow-database https://doi.org/10.5880/fidgeo.2024.014	yes	no
Non-thematic data repositories			
PANGAEA (AWI-managed data repository)	https://www.pangaea.de/	yes	Yes for selected datasets, though this may become more dynamic in the future.
Zenodo (CERN-funded data repository)	https://zenodo.org/	yes	no
Arctic Data Archive System (Japanese data archive)	https://ads.nipr.ac.jp/	yes	yes
Arctic Data Centre (Norwegian Meteorological Institute)	http://arcticdata.met.no/	yes	yes
Italian Arctic Data Center (National Research Council of Italy)	http://arcticnode.dta.cnr.it/cnr/index.php	yes	yes
Polish Polar DataBase (University of Silesia)	https://ppdb.us.edu.pl/	yes	yes
EBAS (NILU)	http://ebas.nilu.no/	yes	yes
Norwegian Marine Data Centre (Institute of Marine Resarch)	http://www.nmdc.no/	yes	yes
Norwegian Polar Data Centre (Norwegian Polar Institute)	http://data.npolar.no/	yes	yes
Norwegian Infrastructure for Research Data Research Data Archive (Funded by Research Council of Norway)	https://archive.sigma2.no/	Yes, for example large digital outcrop models such as Festningen (Betlem and Senger 2022).	Not yet but soon. NIRD RDA is represented in the SIOS data management system working group

References

Betlem P, Senger K (2022) Svalbox-DOM_2020-0001_Festningen [Data set]. <https://doi.org/10.11582/2022.00006>

Hillenbrand IW, Thomson KD, Morgan LE, et al (2023) USGS Geochron: A Database of Geochronological and Thermochemical Dates and Data (ver. 3.0, May 2024)

Koymans MR, van Hinsbergen DJJ, Pastor-Galán D, et al (2020) Towards FAIR Paleomagnetic Data Management Through Paleomagnetism.org 2.0. *Geochem Geophys Geosystems* 21:e2019GC008838. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2019GC008838>

Wu Y, Fang X, Ji J (2023) A global zircon U–Th–Pb geochronological database. *Earth Syst Sci Data* 15:5171–5181. <https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-15-5171-2023>